

Studies on the Complexation Reaction of Dioxouranium(VI) with 3-Hydroxycoumarin

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The reaction of uranyl(II) with 3-hydroxycoumarin is studied in detail by spectrophotometric method. The stepwise formation of two complexes viz., UO_2R^+ and UO_2R_2 , has been established in the pH region studied. The equilibrium constants for 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes have been determined to be 6.48 and 4.14, respectively.

PHENOLS have been studied extensively for their complexation behaviour with metal ions¹⁻³. Dioxouranium forms yellow to orange coloured complexes with phenols. A number of dioxouranium complexes with phenols e.g. kojic acid, catechol⁴, etc. have been studied spectrophotometrically and it has been observed that depending upon pH, 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 complexes are formed in solution. In the present investigation complexation reaction of dioxouranium with 3-hydroxycoumarin has been studied.

Experimental

Stock solution of uranyl ion (0.1 M) containing a few drops of nitric acid to prevent hydrolysis was prepared from $UO_2(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (AnalaR, B.D.H.) and was standardised gravimetrically as oxinate⁵. The ionic strength of solution was maintained constant at 0.1 M using 1 M KNO_3 solution. The pH of the solutions was adjusted using dilute solutions of sodium hydroxide and nitric acid.

3-Hydroxycoumarin (m.p. 153°) was prepared⁶ and crystallised from dilute ethanol.

A Beckman pH-meter model Zeromatic and a Beckman DU-2 spectrophotometer were employed for pH and absorption measurements, respectively.

Method of investigation and calculations :

The system UO_2^{2+} -3-hydroxycoumarin was investigated spectrophotometrically, assuming the following general equilibria in solutions using excess of ligand.

* $x = (ni - Z)$; $y = (ji - q)$

where M = metal ion, H_4R = ligand; MR_nH_x and $MR_{n+j}H_q$ = complexes.

The following straight line equations are then derived⁷⁻¹² and used to interpret the above complexation equilibria.

$$A = \epsilon_1 C_M - [H]^x A / C_R^n K_n \quad \dots (3)$$

$$A = \epsilon_1 C_M + C_R^j (\epsilon_2 C_M - A) K_j / H^j \cdot \alpha^j \quad \dots (4)$$

$$A = \epsilon_2 C_M - [H]^y \alpha^j (A - \epsilon_1 C_M) K_j C_R^j \quad \dots (5)$$

where A = absorption; ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 = molar absorptivity of complexes MR_nH_x and $MR_{n+j}H_q$, respectively; C_M = concentration of the metal; C_R = concentration of the ligand; K_n and K_j = equilibrium constants of complexes MR_nH_x and $MR_{n+j}H_q$, respectively and $\alpha = 1 + K_{a_i} / H \pm 1$ where K_{a_i} = dissociation constant of the ligand.

According to the transformations (3)-(5), various functions such as A vs $A(H)^x$; A vs $(\epsilon_2 C_M - A) / [H]^y \alpha^j$ or A vs $[H]^y \alpha^j / (A - \epsilon_1 C_M)$ are computed from the absorbance at different pH values for solutions with excess of ligand and plotted to get the values of ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 from the limits of these plots. The calculated true values of ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 were put in appropriate logarithmic transformations (6)-(7).

$$\log A / (\epsilon_1 C_M - A) + n \log = n \log C_R + x_p H + \log K_n \quad \dots (6)$$

$$\log (A - \epsilon_1 C_M) / (\epsilon_2 C_M - A) + j \log = j \log C_R + y_p H + \log K_j \quad \dots (7)$$

Accurate values of 'x' and 'y' follow from the slope of these plots for solutions with constant excess of ligand.

A set of pH-absorbance curves was also analysed for corresponding solutions i.e. for solutions having equal values of absorbance $\xi = (A - A_{OR}) / C_M$ (where A_{OR} = absorbance due to ligand). For such conditions simple logarithmic plots i.e. pH vs $-\log C_R$ are valid, whose slopes give directly the ratio of the

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number of coordinated ligands to that of the protons liberated during complexation.

$$pH = \frac{n}{x} (-\log C_R + \log \alpha) + \text{constant} \quad \dots (8)$$

$$pH = \frac{j}{y} (-\log C_R + \log \alpha) + \text{constant} \quad \dots (9)$$

The nuclearity of the complex has been examined, plotting $(A - A_{0R})/C_M = f(pH)$ for various C_M values. The slope of these curves has been found to be independent of the metal ion concentration so that $m-1=0$ and $m=1$ in equation (10). If slope of such plots reaches ' α ', only mononuclear complexes are formed.

$$pH = \frac{m-1}{n} (-\log C_M) + \text{constant} \quad \dots (10)$$

The same forms of transformations (3)-(7) were used for the interpretation of absorbance against the increasing ligand concentration, in excess, keeping pH constant. The number of coordinated ligands was derived from the plots of A_j vs A/C_R^n , A vs $C_R^j / (\epsilon_2 C_M - A)$ or A vs $(A - \epsilon_1 C_M) / C_R^j$.

Results and Discussion

Aqueous solution of dioxouranium gives orange coloured complex on mixing methanolic solution of 3-hydroxycoumarin. The absorption of the complex remains constant for more than 24 hr. The complexation reaction is reversible within the pH range 1.0-6.5. The reaction, however, is not reversible at $pH \geq 6.5$. Subsequent studies have, therefore, been limited upto pH 6.5 only.

pH-Absorbance curves: A family of curves (Fig. 1) was obtained at λ_{max} 390 nm with variations in ligand concentration but at fixed concentration of the metal ion. These curves, obtained at different pH values keeping C_R^n and C_R^j constant, were analysed supposing general equilibria (1)-(2), by means of transformations (3)-(5) (Fig. 2). Molar absorptivities of the two complexes were then obtained from this figure by the method of successive approximation.

Comparable values of ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 have also been obtained from the plots of A vs A/C_R^n and A vs $C_R^j / (\epsilon_2 C_M - A)$ at constant pH values (Fig. 3).

The above calculated values of ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 were put in appropriate logarithmic transformation (6)-(7) and plots of pH vs $\log A / (A_{01} - A)$ and pH vs $\log (A - A_{01}) / (A_{02} - A)$ were found almost equal to unity and thus values of ' x ' and ' y ' were obtained.

Sets of pH-absorbance curves were further analysed using equations (6)-(9) for the method of corresponding solutions. From the slope of the curves pH vs $-\log C_R$, comparable values of ' x ' and ' y ' have been obtained.

It can thus be inferred that under different pH intervals, one molecule of 3-hydroxycoumarin is successively coordinated in the two steps with the

Fig. 1. pH-Absorbance curves of UO_2^{2+} -3-hydroxycoumarin complex at various ligand concentrations. Wave length = 390 nm ; $C_M = 4 \times 10^{-5} M$; $C_R = Y \cdot 10^{-4} M$ ($Y = 4, 5, 8, 12$ and 16 for curves 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5, respectively).

Fig. 2. Analysis of pH-absorbance curves. X for curves 1-5 = $A(H) \cdot 10^6$; for curves 6-10 = $(A - A_{01}) \cdot 10^6$ and for curves 11-15 = $(A_{02} - AO) / [H] \cdot 2.10^{-4}$.

liberation of the only proton in each step of complexation upto pH 6.5. The following course of the reaction is suggested.

Fig. 3. Analysis of pH-absorption curves. for 'x'-y' axis-absorption ligand concentration plots $C_R = Y \cdot 10^{-5} M$ (Y=4, 5, 8, 12, 16) $N = A/C_R$, pH for curves 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5=4.0, 4.4, 4.5, 4.75 and 5.0, respectively. For 'A'-B' axis-absorption ligand concentration plots $K = (A - A_{01})/C_R$. pH for curves 7, 8, 9 and 6=6.0, 6.2, 6.5 and 5.8, respectively.

The composition of the above complexes has also been established at different wave lengths (390, 400 and 420 nm) using Job's method of continuous variations keeping $C_0 = 2.10^{-4} M$.

From the pH-absorbance plots, it is deduced that the above mentioned complexes are formed in different pH intervals indicated in Table 1.

C_R	pH	
	Equilibrium(11)	Equilibrium(12)
$4.10^{-4} M$	4.10-5.60	6.10-6.50
$5.10^{-4} M$	3.90-5.45	5.85-6.50
$8.10^{-4} M$	3.70-5.30	5.70-6.50
$12.10^{-4} M$	3.60-5.10	5.50-6.50
$16.10^{-4} M$	3.40-5.00	5.40-6.50

Equilibrium constants of complexes: The dissociation constant (K_{a1}) of the ligand, 3-hydroxy-coumarin, determined pH-metrically was found to be 7.90.

The equilibrium constants of UO_2R^+ and UO_2R_2 complexes (Table 2) were calculated from the following equations.

$$\log A / (\epsilon_1 C_M - A) \left(1 + \frac{K_{a1}}{[H]} \right) = pH + \log C_R + \log K_1 \quad \dots (13)$$

$$\log (A - \epsilon_1 C_M) / (\epsilon_2 C_M - A) \left(1 + \frac{K_{a1}}{[H]} \right) = pH + \log C_R + \log K_2 \quad \dots (14)$$

TABLE 2—EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS FOR VARIOUS DIOXOURANIUM COMPLEXES WITH 3-HYDROXYCOUMARIN

Equilibrium constant	Equilibrium
$k_1 = -1.42$	$\frac{[MR][H]}{[M][HR]}$
$k_2 = -3.76$	$\frac{[MR_2][H]}{[MR][HR]}$
$K_1 = 6.48$	$\frac{[MR]}{[M][R]}$
$K_2 = 4.14$	$\frac{[MR_2]}{[MR][R]}$

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